

PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF WHOLESALE TRADE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *With the development of industrial production in Uzbekistan, the importance of wholesale trade in the field of their exchange is growing. Today, the problems of wholesale trade development in Uzbekistan are related to the fact that the trade infrastructure does not meet modern requirements. This article highlights some of the challenges in developing wholesale infrastructure. Practical recommendations have been developed to address the identified problems.*

Keywords: *wholesale trade, wholesale infrastructure, warehousing, logistics, marketing, free trade zone, international trade.*

Introduction

Today's fierce competition is characterized by significant changes in the infrastructure of commodity markets. In particular, the wholesale-distribution system is changing with new structures, new forms of wholesale trade. In addition, there is a high saturation of commodity markets, high innovative activity of enterprises in the fight for the buyer. This means that manufacturers need to be engaged not only in developing new ideas for the delivery of goods, but also in developing methods that reduce costs in delivering goods to the final consumer.

One of the key factors in this situation is to increase the efficiency of distribution channels. This requires the establishment of long-term and mutually beneficial wholesale trade relations between manufacturers, intermediaries and retailers based on business relationships. One of the most pressing problems hindering the development of the wholesale trade sector in Uzbekistan is the underdeveloped trade infrastructure.

Therefore, the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026 sets the task of establishing 130 modern markets and trade complexes, as well as 65 large and 5,000 small service facilities for the development of road infrastructure through the development of trade and road services in the regions of the Republic. obtained.

The main part

Wholesale trade is the most important sector of the commodity market infrastructure. The organization of wholesale trade channels and the joint activities of banks is a field of activity that ensures the effective functioning of the system of commodity-money circulation. In addition to being an important component of the wholesale commodity markets, there must also be a certain infrastructure for it to function as an independent activity.

The trade infrastructure formed before the 1990s could not meet the demand for free market relations. The trade infrastructure includes not only basic infrastructure facilities such as roads, ports, warehouses, retail outlets, power supply networks, but also service infrastructure for the trade sector, including the availability of the required number of highly developed logistics companies, distributors and wholesale suppliers, certifiers and licensors. organizations, companies operating in the advertising market, educational institutions.

When trading activity is rationally organized, it contributes to the optimization of production and commercial activities, expansion of its scale and efficiency, the study of risk factors, reliable forecasting of the future with fairly clear guidelines for the desired economic success.

In our opinion, the main problems formation, functioning and development of wholesale trade should include:

1. Reduction of the role and underestimation of the importance of wholesale trade as an effective and efficient organizer of the movement of goods and distribution of commodity resources.

2. Problems in the field of service infrastructure include weak economic links between producers and trade organizations: insufficient development of cooperation, the presence of many intermediaries between small producers and small trade organizations.

3. Fragmentation of wholesale trade structures, their insufficient provision with modern warehouses and technologies for warehouse processing of goods. All this leads to the fact that a certain number of wholesalers do not have the capacity at a sufficient level and in the required volume to perform their functions, therefore, they are transferred to intermediaries for execution.

4. Non-compliance of the existing wholesale trade services with the modern requirements of the main consumers of these services (manufacturers of consumer goods and buyers), this is reflected in the fact that:

manufacturing enterprises are interested in rapid and large-scale penetration into the market (territorial coverage, presence of the main product range and rapid change in assortment, occupying space on store shelves), as well as in effective management of overdue receivables debt;

trade requires a rational system of commodity supply within a significant list of assortment positions, which is able to offer the optimal number of additional services (storage and transportation of goods, credit for purchasing operations, advertising, information and marketing support, etc.).

The world experience of trade development shows that wholesale trade remains an important link in the consumer market. In developed economies, there is a clear mechanism for the development of wholesale trade, and similar trends in their activities, systemic and organizational decisions are specific to a particular stage of economic development.

At present, the main directions in the development of wholesale trade in foreign countries are concentration and diversification. There is a merger of independent wholesale enterprises, the organization of wholesale and retail trade in the structure of industrial enterprises, the expansion of the network of major trade intermediaries, the merger of wholesale trade structures. However, the position of small wholesale structures is not weakened.

The development of a new concept for the development of wholesale trade in Uzbekistan is a requirement of modern economic development. On the basis of digitalization of full sales operations and warehousing, improvement of logistics and marketing services, it is necessary to establish wholesale trade enterprises that will provide a smooth supply of retail goods, provide comprehensive services to customers, ensure uninterrupted product movement in sectors of the economy.

Conclusion

The purpose of the development of wholesale trade is to create distribution channels for large domestic producers, to create favorable conditions for suppliers to enter foreign markets. Conclusions on the development of wholesale trade infrastructure are as follows:

1. The creation of appropriate infrastructure institutions is a factor in the formation of free market relations. Among them, regional wholesale markets play an important role. The level of development of infrastructure institutions in the field of wholesale trade today does not fully meet the modern requirements of trade turnover in Uzbekistan. The current situation implies the

creation of an infrastructure that will deliver goods more efficiently from producer to consumer.

Wholesale infrastructure is a set of material, technological, organizational, informational, legal and social facilities that provide wholesale trade activities. The structure of the wholesale market consists of producers and suppliers of goods. Such infrastructure has a complete cycle that organizes the production, processing, distribution, sale and marketing of goods.

2. It is expedient to establish specialized wholesale infrastructure in each sector of the economy. Wholesale infrastructure should include access roads, warehouses, laboratories, production and storage facilities, car parks, refrigerated containers for wet fruits and vegetables.

3. In addition, the prerequisites for solving problems that hinder the development of wholesale trade should be equal investment in wholesale trade facilities by the state and private businesses, the creation of an effective logical system, and the introduction of modern storage technologies. The intensive application of the principles of logistics will make it possible to establish a system of supply, packaging, storage, transportation and sale of goods - this contributes to the transformation of wholesale trade into an effective one supply system and customer service.

4. One of the important factors in ensuring the successful operation of the wholesale market is the development of information supply. The main purpose of the information and communication system of the wholesale market is to effectively coordinate the production, distribution and sale of goods on the basis of complete and reliable information on market needs, status and opportunities. Wholesale commodity markets can respond to changes in supply and sales regimes using data on production volume and number of consumers. Makes decisions on expanding wholesale trade infrastructure.

5. The organization of wholesale markets is also considered in the system of vertical integral formations of industries. Wholesale markets combine the turnover of processing enterprises, wholesalers and consumers and ensure the development of infrastructure. Wholesale markets established in the regions eliminate informal intermediaries, provide incentives to commodity producers, help minimize production costs and adhere to quality standards. Within the framework of this integration, a large part of the goods will be sold.

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